

Navigating Tax Dynamics Through an In-Depth Simulation of Vat Rate Changes on Consumer Spending Patterns in Nigeria

Adesina, Omotoyosi Esther

Department of Business Administration, University of Lagos

Abstract:

This study examines the relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) rates and consumer spending patterns in Nigeria using a quantitative research approach. This research design explores the possible impacts of variations in VAT rates on consumer spending patterns using a Monte Carlo simulation technique. Secondary data from reliable sources, from the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), are analyzed over a 12-year period (2011-2022) to investigate trends in consumer spending and VAT rates. The findings show a positive linear relationship between VAT rates and consumer spending, indicating that changes in VAT policy can significantly influence consumer spending patterns and the growth of the economy as a whole. A descriptive analysis of VAT rates and consumer spending across the research period reveals increasing trends in consumer spending, with fluctuations in VAT rates. Monte Carlo simulation analysis provides insights into the range of potential consumer spending outcomes under different VAT rate scenarios, which captures the uncertainty associated with anticipating consumer behaviour in response to policy changes. Sensitivity analyses further demonstrate the impact of varying VAT rate increments (5%, 10%, and 20%) on consumer spending patterns, emphasizing the importance for

policymakers to carefully consider how changing VAT policy will affect both

consumer spending and the overall economy. Overall, this study contributes to the understanding of how changes in VAT rates impact consumer spending patterns in Nigeria, providing insightful information to decision-makers, academics, and stakeholders who are involved in the development of economic policies.

Keywords: Simulation, Monte Carlo, Consumer Spending, Value Added Tax

Introduction:

1.1 Background to the Study:

Value Added Tax (VAT) is a key element of fiscal policy in many countries, including Nigeria, where it was introduced in 1993 to diversify government revenue sources. Recognized as a vital tool for economic management, VAT influences consumer spending patterns and has undergone several changes to align with government objectives and economic policies. The initial VAT rate of 5% was increased to 7.5% in February 2020, reflecting shifts in economic priorities. VAT has become an essential source of income for the Nigerian government, significantly contributing to national finances.

Understanding the dynamics of VAT is crucial, especially regarding its impact on consumer spending as Nigeria strives for economic growth. Numerous studies have explored the relationship between VAT and economic factors, emphasizing its effects on development and growth. However,

complexities in tax planning and administration remain, necessitating a thorough understanding of these issues to support economic stability.

Consumer spending is closely linked to tax policies, and research has highlighted the need to examine how changes in VAT rates affect consumption. Theoretical frameworks on consumption patterns, developed by scholars like Deaton and Friedman, provide insights into individual spending decisions. This study aims to simulate VAT rate changes and their effects on consumer spending patterns in Nigeria, contributing to the understanding of VAT's implications for economic growth.

1.2 Statement of the Problem:

Taxation policies, particularly VAT, play a crucial role in shaping fiscal plans and influencing consumer spending in Nigeria. Despite several modifications to VAT rates and regulations, the specific implications of these changes on consumer spending patterns remain under explored. Existing literature emphasizes the connection between VAT and consumption, but a comprehensive understanding of how variations in VAT rates affect consumer decisions is lacking.

This study seeks to address these research gaps by investigating the complex dynamics of VAT and its impact on consumer spending. Policymakers and tax authorities need to understand consumer responses to VAT changes to make informed decisions. The relevance of this research is underscored by the evolving economic environment and the behavioural effects of VAT rate changes. While previous studies have examined domestic taxes and international trade, focused research on VAT's implications for consumer spending in Nigeria is limited.

This study aims to provide detailed insights into how VAT rate adjustments affect different demographic groups and

economic sectors, capturing the diversity of consumer responses across urban and rural areas. Ultimately, the research will contribute to evidence-based policy choices that promote sustainable development and economic growth in Nigeria.

1.3 Aim and objectives of the study:

The study aims to have an in-depth simulation of Value Added Tax (VAT) rate changes on consumer spending patterns in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. simulates the effects of varying VAT rates on consumer spending patterns.
- ii. determine the factors that influence consumer spending patterns in response to VAT rate changes.
- iii. identify key variables that significantly influence the outcomes of the simulation.
- iv. to determine the potential policy implications of the observed patterns in consumer choices

1.4 Research Questions:

To guide the study, the following research questions are put forward:

- i. how do changes in VAT rates affect consumer spending patterns in Nigeria using a simulation model?
- ii. what factors influence consumer spending patterns in response to adjustments in VAT rates?
- iii. what are the key variables that significantly influence the outcomes of the simulation model?
- iv. what are the potential policy implications of the observed patterns in consumer choices?

1.5 Research Hypothesis:

The study is to test the null hypothesis that changes in VAT rates have no significant impact on consumer spending patterns in Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the Study:

This research is significant for policymakers, tax authorities, and

economists involved in fiscal policy formulation in Nigeria. By exploring the relationship between value-added tax (VAT) rate changes and consumer purchasing patterns, the study aims to enhance the effectiveness of tax policy and stimulate economic growth. The findings provide essential insights for policymakers regarding how changes in VAT rates influence consumer spending. This understanding can assist in crafting equitable tax policies that consider both consumer welfare and revenue generation.

Additionally, businesses can utilize the research outcomes to adjust their pricing strategies, product offerings, and marketing efforts in response to VAT fluctuations, thereby boosting their sustainability and competitiveness. Furthermore, the study highlights the unequal impacts of VAT on various demographic groups and economic sectors, contributing to the development of fair tax policies that promote income redistribution, poverty alleviation, and overall socioeconomic well-being.

1.7 Scope of the Study:

This study focuses on VAT rate changes and their impact on consumer spending patterns in Nigeria. The study considers various demographic groups, including but not limited to low-income households, middle-class consumers, and high-income individuals, to understand how VAT rate changes affect different segments of the population.

The study proposes the development and utilization of a Monte Carlo simulation model to analyze the effects of VAT rate changes on consumer spending patterns. This model integrates VAT rate adjustments and consumer expenditure parameters to simulate various scenarios and predict their outcomes accurately.

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

A thorough conceptual review is essential to understand the complexities of VAT policy and its impact on consumer spending patterns.

• Consumer Spending Patterns

Consumer spending patterns are influenced by various factors, including individual and macroeconomic determinants. Income levels are crucial, as highlighted by Deaton (2001) and Friedman (1957), who argue that disposable income significantly affects consumer behaviour. The marginal propensity to consume (MPC) and income elasticity are key concepts that describe how changes in income influence spending.

Demographic factors such as age, gender, and household composition also shape spending habits. For instance, higher-income families may exhibit different spending patterns compared to lower-income households. Cultural backgrounds further influence expenditure priorities.

The relationship between VAT rates and consumer spending is a topic of interest. Gelardi (2012) emphasizes the need to understand consumer reactions to tax policy changes, noting that VAT rate adjustments can directly affect prices and indirectly influence consumer confidence and economic conditions.

• Factors Influencing Consumer Spending Patterns

Several factors impact consumer spending, including disposable income, inflation rates, interest rates, and government policies. Variations in disposable income across income categories and regions significantly affect spending behaviour in Nigeria. Inflation can diminish purchasing power, while low inflation may enhance consumer confidence and spending. Gelardi (2012) underscores the importance of understanding consumer behaviour in response to tax policy changes, as VAT rate

adjustments can influence perceptions of affordability and purchasing decisions.

- **Tax Policies**

Tax policies, particularly VAT rates, significantly shape consumer behaviour and economic activity. Nasiru et al. (2016) assess the impact of VAT on Nigeria's economic growth, highlighting how changes in VAT rates can alter spending behaviours by affecting the costs of goods and services. Increased VAT rates may reduce purchasing power, while lower rates can stimulate demand. Effective tax planning and administration are vital for successful tax policies, as noted by Appah (2010) and Nwaobia (2013). Transparent tax policies enhance taxpayer confidence and compliance, improving revenue collection and economic stability. Obiakor et al. (2015) examine the relationship between VAT and consumer spending patterns, indicating that changes in VAT rates can influence household purchasing decisions. James and Asaama (2012) emphasize the significance of tax policies for economic growth and revenue generation, as fluctuations in VAT rates can impact government revenue and overall fiscal policy.

- **Value Added Tax (VAT)**

Value Added Tax (VAT) is a crucial element of modern taxation systems worldwide. As noted by Bird (2005), VAT has been widely adopted since the 1950s, particularly in European Union countries. Adereti et al. (2011) examine VAT's impact on economic growth and its role in government revenue generation, while Gelardi (2012) explores the direct relationship between VAT and consumer spending patterns.

As a consumption tax, VAT directly affects the prices of goods and services purchased by individuals and businesses. Changes in VAT rates can influence consumer behaviour by altering the affordability of

products, thereby impacting overall spending patterns. Adereti et al. (2011) emphasize VAT as a significant revenue source for governments, highlighting the importance of understanding its effects on consumer spending and economic activity.

- **Simulation Model**

Simulation modeling, as discussed by Sharma (2016), is a valuable tool for analyzing the potential effects of VAT rate changes on consumer spending in Nigeria. This approach allows decision-makers to evaluate how different tax policy options influence consumer behaviour and economic outcomes. By considering various economic factors and policy variables, simulation models provide insights into the dynamic relationship between VAT rate changes and consumer spending.

The limited use of simulation modeling in the context of Nigerian VAT highlights the need for further exploration of this methodology. Policymakers can utilize simulation models to assess various VAT scenarios and their potential impacts on consumer spending, GDP growth, inflation, and other key economic indicators. Sensitivity analysis through simulation helps identify risks and uncertainties, enabling informed policy decisions.

2.2 Theoretical Review:

Theoretical reviews enhance academic understanding by clarifying the principles guiding the study.

- **Life-Cycle Permanent Income Hypothesis**

Proposed by Hall (2001), this hypothesis emphasizes long-term income expectations over current income levels, providing a framework for analyzing consumer spending patterns. It suggests that consumers adjust their borrowing and saving behaviours to maintain stable consumption, even when VAT rate changes

affect disposable income. Studies by Deaton (2001) and Gelardi (2012) further explore the factors influencing consumer spending decisions, supporting the relevance of this hypothesis in understanding VAT's impact on spending.

- **Theory of the Consumption Function**

Developed by Milton Friedman (1957), this theory explains the relationship between consumer spending and disposable income. Friedman posits that changes in disposable income proportionately affect consumption levels, with the Marginal Propensity to Consume (MPC) being a key concept. In the context of VAT rate changes in Nigeria, this theory provides insights into how fluctuations in disposable income influence consumer spending patterns. Although direct citations of Friedman's theory are limited, its core ideas remain essential for understanding consumer responses to VAT adjustments, as discussed by Gelardi (2012).

- **Intertemporal Choice Theory**

Intertemporal choice theory integrates concepts from economics, psychology, and behavioural economics, with early contributions from Irving Fisher, who explored its implications for interest rates and investment in his 1930 work, "The Theory of Interest." This theory examines how individuals make decisions by balancing immediate satisfaction against delayed rewards, considering factors like impulsiveness, discounting, and self-control (Takahashi & Han, 2012). Time preferences reflect individuals' inclination toward immediate gratification over future rewards, influencing decision-making. Discounting is a key concept, indicating how people value future rewards less than immediate ones, often quantified by discount functions (Takahashi & Han, 2012).

This theory applies to various real-world scenarios, including financial decision-

making and health behaviour, where individuals weigh current spending against future needs (Thaler, 2008). Understanding intertemporal choice is vital for designing public policies that promote long-term welfare, such as incentives for education or retirement savings.

2.3 Empirical Review:

Empirical studies by Adereti et al. (2011) and Nasiru et al. (2016) provide valuable insights into the relationship between value-added taxation (VAT) and economic growth in Nigeria. Adereti et al. (2011) find that VAT positively contributes to economic growth, while Nasiru et al. (2016) demonstrate a correlation between VAT systems and economic outcomes, highlighting the broader macroeconomic effects of VAT rate adjustments.

James and Asaama (2012) offer empirical data on the relationship between VAT and consumer spending, showing how varying VAT rates influence consumer choices and spending patterns. This study builds on their findings, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive investigation into how VAT rate variations affect different consumer industry sectors.

Appah (2010) explores the challenges in tax administration and planning in Nigeria, offering insights into the practical obstacles faced by tax authorities in implementing VAT regulations. His findings inform the current study's approach to evaluating VAT rate adjustments and formulating policy recommendations.

Empirical research by Nwaobia (2013) and Matthew (2014) examines the connection between corporate financial performance and VAT regulations. Nwaobia (2013) focuses on the impact of tax planning on business performance, while Matthew (2014) looks at the broader effects of tax collection on the Nigerian economy. These studies provide a foundation for

understanding the interplay between VAT rate changes, corporate performance, and economic growth.

Fasoranti (2009) adds a socioeconomic dimension through an empirical investigation of rural spending patterns, revealing how demographic factors influence responses to VAT rate changes. Keen and Syed (2006) contribute to this discourse by examining the challenges posed by digital platforms and international trade on VAT administration, offering insights into the impact of modern technology on tax practices.

Thaler's (2008) work in behavioral economics introduces the role of heuristics in decision-making, providing a behavioral perspective on how psychological factors may affect consumer responses to VAT changes. Finally, studies by Randall (2010) and Matthew (2014) underscore the importance of VAT in tax revenue collection, highlighting the fiscal impact of VAT policies on government budgets.

2.4 Gaps in Literature:

Identifying gaps in the literature is essential for guiding future research. While the effects of VAT on economic variables in Nigeria are documented, there is a lack of studies specifically examining how VAT rate variations affect consumer spending patterns. Current research often focuses on macroeconomic impacts or business operations rather than direct consumer responses.

Additionally, empirical studies analysing consumer reactions to VAT rate changes in Nigeria are scarce. Although theoretical frameworks like Friedman's permanent income hypothesis offer insights, empirical data on how consumers adjust their spending in response to VAT changes is limited. More research is needed to understand the mechanisms through which

VAT rate variations influence purchasing decisions.

Furthermore, while simulation modelling has been widely used in economic research, its application to studying VAT rate changes and consumer spending patterns in Nigeria is underexplored. Incorporating simulation methodologies could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the potential effects of VAT modifications on consumer behaviour. Addressing these gaps will enhance our understanding of the relationship between VAT rate changes and consumer spending patterns in Nigeria, aiding stakeholders and policymakers in making informed decisions regarding VAT policy adjustments.

Methodology:

3.1 Research Design:

This study adopts a quantitative research design, by utilizing a Monte Carlo simulation approach. By sampling input variables at random, the Monte Carlo simulation makes it possible to model complicated systems and investigate different scenarios. This design can be used to evaluate the possible effects of changes in the VAT rate on the spending patterns of Nigerian consumers.

3.2 Population of the Study:

This study takes into account a wide range of income levels, demographics, and economics sector to represent the total Nigerian consumer community to depict the rate of consumer spending patterns about changes in the VAT rate.

3.3 Data Collection Method:

For this study, secondary data from the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) was used through extraction and compilation. Getting historical data on VAT rates and patterns of consumer spending is the main goal in providing information for the Monte Carlo simulation. To account for uncertainties,

the simulation introduces a random error term and incorporates the linear relationship between VAT rates and consumer spending.

3.4 Validity and reliability of research instrument

The data collected were carefully designed to correspond with the study objectives, ensuring the validity of the research instrument. By thorough testing against historical data, the Monte Carlo simulation model's reliability is determined. To improve the model's consistency and predictive ability while simulating consumer spending pattern under various VAT rates scenarios, it is iteratively modified.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis:

The Monte Carlo simulation model was developed using Excel Spread Sheet, to simulate several scenarios of VAT rate changes and their consequences on consumer spending patterns, the model includes consumer spending pattern parameters and adjustments to the VAT rate. The simulation model generated several scenarios with varying VAT rate adjustments, including variations in the amount and timing of rate changes.

Descriptive statistical techniques, including measures of central tendency, dispersion, and variability, were used to summarize consumer spending data under different VAT rate scenarios. Graphical representations were also employed to visualize the attribution of consumer spending pattern metrics.

3.6 Model Specification

The Monte Carlo simulation modeling incorporates a random error element to represent real-world uncertainties and assumes a linear relationship between VAT rates and consumer spending. By creating random samples of VAT rates and computing the accompanying consumer spending values for each sample, the Monte Carlo simulation was used to examine a wide variety of possible outcomes. The findings are aggregated over a large number of simulations.

The dependent variable is **Consumer Spending (CS)**, representing the aggregate expenditure by consumers in the Nigerian economy. The independent variable is **VAT Rate (V)**, denoting the percentage imposed on the value added to goods and services at each stage of production and distribution.

The mathematical model employed in this study is expressed as:

The mathematical model employed in this study is expressed as:

$$CS = m \cdot V + c + e$$

where:

- CS is the Consumer Spending,
- V is the VAT Rate,
- m is the slope of the relationship,
- c is the intercept,
- e is the random error term.

Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Presentation of Historical Data

These datasets were carefully compiled and sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) respectively, which serve as essential components in the empirical analysis of how changes in VAT rates may influence consumer spending over the years.

Table 4.1: Final Consumption Spending of Households for the last 12 years (2011-2022)

Year	Amount (N'Billion)
2011	41,437.72
2012	42,115.91
2013	58,745.85
2014	63,524.49
2015	74,410.95
2016	83,218.22
2017	91,599.98
2018	98,392.13
2019	108,085.82
2020	97,718.07
2021	108,468.24
2022	130,077.62

Table 4.2: Value Added Tax (VAT) Report Collected by the Federal Inland

Year	Amount (N'Billion)
2011	4,628.48
2012	5,007.65
2013	4,805.64
2014	4,714.56
2015	3,741.76
2016	3,307.46
2017	4,027.95
2018	5,320.89
2019	5,261.92
2020	4,952.22
2021	6,402.71
2022	10,179.35

Source: Planning, Research and Statistics Department, FIRS

Table 4.3: Summary Statistics of Consumer Spending and VAT Rate

	Consumer Spending	VAT Rate
Mean	83149.58493	5195.88225
Standard Deviation	27735.39357	1762.146652
No. of years	12	12

Consumer Spending: The analysis of consumer spending over the 12 years

Figure 4.1: Graphical Representation of Consumer Spending of Households

Revenue Service, for the last 12 years (2011-2022)

Figure 4.2: Graphical Representation of Value-added Tax Rate

reveals several key insights. The average consumer spending during this period was

approximately ₦83.15 billion, with a variability represented by a standard deviation of approximately ₦27.74 billion.

Tax Rate: The examination of tax rates over the same period provides insights into the financial landscape. The average tax rate during the 12 years was approximately ₦5.196 billion, with a standard deviation of approximately ₦1.762 billion.

4.3 Monte Carlo Simulation of Consumer Spending

Table 4.4: Summary Statistics of the Simulated Consumer Spending

<i>Simulated consumer spending</i>	
Number of Iterations	1000
Mean	84677.57318
Standard Deviation	1729.298936
Skewness	-0.128159345
Kurtosis	-0.005931723
Minimum	79393.48553
Maximum	89838.43597

The Monte Carlo simulation, conducted with 1,000 iterations, offers key insights into potential consumer spending patterns in Nigeria under varying VAT rates. The average simulated consumer spending was estimated at ₦84,677.57 billion, with a standard deviation of ₦1,729.30 billion, indicating variability around the mean.

The distribution of consumer spending showed a slight negative skew (skewness: -0.128), suggesting a minor tendency toward lower-than-average spending values. The kurtosis of -0.006 indicated a platykurtic distribution, characterized by a flatter peak and thinner tails than a normal distribution, implying fewer extreme values.

The observed minimum and maximum simulated consumer spending values were approximately ₦79,393.49 billion and ₦89,838.44 billion, respectively.

Figure 4.3: Graphical representation of Simulated Consumer Spending

4.4 Linear Relationship Analysis

The linear relationship between VAT rates (V) and consumer spending (CS) is modeled as:

$$CS = 9.295098562 * V + 34853.3473 + e$$

Here, the slope of 9.2951 represents the expected increase in consumer spending for every one-unit increase in the VAT rate. This positive slope indicates a direct relationship: as VAT rates rise, consumer spending is expected to increase correspondingly. Specifically, consumer spending is projected to increase by approximately ₦9.2951 billion for each unit increase in the VAT rate.

The intercept of 34,853.35 represents the estimated consumer spending when the VAT rate is zero, although this scenario is rarely encountered in practice. Thus, while the intercept serves as a reference point for the model, its practical relevance is limited.

Understanding this linear relationship is crucial for policymakers and researchers in assessing the impact of VAT policy changes on consumer spending and broader

economic activity. By using economic models and simulations, policymakers can explore different VAT rate scenarios and their effects on spending patterns, aiding in the optimization of VAT policies to achieve targeted economic outcomes and support evidence-based decision-making.

4.5 Test of Hypothesis:

To get insight into the relationship between changes in the VAT rate and consumer spending patterns in Nigeria, it is essential to perform a sensitivity analysis. This analysis is essential to assessing the validity and consistency of our results, particularly when considering multiple scenarios.

4.5.1 Sensitivity Analysis: Simulation of 5% increment to VAT rate

The purpose of the sensitivity analysis is to determine how Nigerian consumer spending patterns might be affected by a 5% increase in the VAT rate. Our goal in performing this sensitivity analysis is to assess the reliability and consistency of our results in the context of potential changes to VAT policy.

Table 4.5: VAT Rate (5% Increment) Amount (₦' Billion)

Year	Consumer Spending	VAT Rate (5% Increment)
2011	41,437.72	4859.90
2012	42,115.91	5258.04
2013	58,745.85	5045.92
2014	63,524.49	4950.29
2015	74,410.95	3928.85
2016	83,218.22	3472.83
2017	91,599.98	4229.34
2018	98,392.13	5586.94
2019	108,085.82	5525.01
2020	97,718.07	5199.84
2021	108,468.24	6722.85
2022	130,077.62	10688.32

Table 4.6: Summary Statistics of VAT Rate (5% Increment)

	VAT Rate
Mean	5455.676363
Standard Deviation	1850.253984
No. of years	12

The provided summary statistics indicate an average Value Added Tax (VAT) rate of approximately ₦5455.68 billion, with a standard deviation of around ₦1850.25billion, over the 12years, considering a 5% increment.

Figure 4.4: Graphical Representation of VAT Rate (5% Increment)

Table 4.7: Summary Statistics of the Simulated Consumer Spending (5% Increment)

<i>Simulated consumer spending</i>	
Number of Iterations	1000
Mean	83335.08765
Standard Deviation	1841.973266
Kurtosis	0.063985387
Skewness	-0.060296786
Minimum	77724.75941
Maximum	88861.62928

4.5.1(a): Interpretation of Data

The sensitivity analysis, performed with 1,000 iterations, examines consumer spending patterns in response to a 5% increase in VAT rates, measured in billion

Naira. The analysis reveals an average consumer spending of ₦83,335.09 billion. The standard deviation of approximately ₦1,841.97 billion indicates moderate variability around this mean.

The kurtosis value of 0.06 suggests a slightly leptokurtic distribution, meaning there is a somewhat higher probability of extreme values or outliers. The slight negative skewness of approximately -0.06 indicates a minor tendency towards lower spending values, reflecting subtle changes in consumer spending.

The minimum and maximum simulated consumer spending values provide a comprehensive view of the potential range of outcomes, supporting the study’s goal of understanding how VAT rate changes impact consumer spending patterns.

4.5.1 (b): Changes in Linear relationship

The sensitivity analysis results indicate a need to adjust the linear relationship model to reflect the impact of a 5% increase in VAT rates. The revised model, accounting for this adjustment, is represented as:

$$CS=8.852474821 * V+34853.3473+e$$

In this updated model, the slope has been adjusted to 8.8525, representing the new rate of change in consumer spending for each unit increase in the VAT rate. This change reflects how the consumer spending response to VAT rate variations has evolved.

The intercept remains at 34,853.35, representing the estimated consumer spending when the VAT rate is zero. Since the adjustment pertains only to the VAT rate’s effect, the intercept value remains unchanged.

Figure 4.5: Graphical representation of Simulated Consumer Spending (5% Increment)

4.5.2 Sensitivity Analysis: Simulation of 10% increment to VAT rate

The purpose of the sensitivity analysis is to determine how Nigerian consumer spending patterns might be affected by a 10% increase in the VAT rate. Our goal in performing this sensitivity analysis is to assess the reliability and consistency of our results in the context of potential changes to VAT policy.

Table 4.8: VAT Rate (10% Increment) Amount (₦’Billion)

Year	Consumer Spending	VAT Rate (10% Increment)
2011	41,437.72	5091.32
2012	42,115.91	5508.42
2013	58,745.85	5286.21
2014	63,524.49	5186.02
2015	74,410.95	4115.93
2016	83,218.22	3638.21
2017	91,599.98	4430.74
2018	98,392.13	5852.98
2019	108,085.82	5788.11
2020	97,718.07	5447.45
2021	108,468.24	7042.98
2022	130,077.62	11197.29

Table 4.9: Summary Statistics of VAT Rate (10% Increment)

	VAT Rate
Mean	5715.470475
Standard Deviation	1938.361317
No. of years	12

The provided summary statistics indicate an average Value Added Tax (VAT) rate of approximately ₦5715.47 billion, with a standard deviation of around ₦1938.36billion, over the 12years, considering a 10% increment.

Figure 4.6: Graphical Representation of VAT Rate (10% Increment)

Table 4.10: Summary Statistics of the Simulated Consumer Spending (10% Increment)

<i>Simulated consumer spending</i>	
Number of Iterations	1000
Mean	83717.009
Standard Deviation	1932.717101
Kurtosis	0.239817725
Skewness	-0.195166783
Minimum	77193.88938
Maximum	89642.00456

4.5.2 (a): Interpretation of Data

The sensitivity analysis, conducted with 1,000 iterations, evaluates consumer spending patterns in response to a 10% increase in VAT rates. The estimated mean simulated consumer spending is approximately ₦83,717.01 billion, providing a key indicator of average consumer expenditure under these conditions.

The standard deviation of ₦1,932.72 billion highlights the variation in consumer spending values around the mean.

The kurtosis value of approximately 0.24 indicates a slightly leptokurtic distribution, suggesting a higher likelihood of extreme values or outliers. The observed rightward skewness of about 0.08 reflects a slight deviation from perfect symmetry in the distribution of spending outcomes.

4.5.2 (b): Changes in Linear relationship

The sensitivity analysis results necessitate an adjustment to the linear relationship model to reflect the effects of a 10% increase in VAT rates. The revised model is expressed as:

$$CS = 8.4500896 * V + 34853.3473 + e$$

In this updated model, the slope is adjusted to 8.4501, indicating the new rate of change in consumer spending for each unit increase in the VAT rate. This modification accounts for the expected impact of the VAT rate increase.

The intercept remains at 34,853.35, representing the estimated consumer spending when the VAT rate is zero. Since the adjustment pertains solely to the VAT rate's effect, the intercept value is unchanged.

Figure 4.7: Graphical representation of Simulated Consumer Spending (10% Increment)

4.5.3 Sensitivity Analysis: Simulation of 20% increment to VAT rate

The purpose of the sensitivity analysis is to determine how Nigerian consumer spending patterns might be affected by a 20% increase in the VAT rate. Our goal in performing this sensitivity analysis is to assess the reliability and consistency of our results in the context of potential changes to VAT policy.

Table 4.11: VAT Rate (20% Increment) Amount (₦' Billion)

Year	Consumer Spending	VAT Rate	VAT Rate (20% Increment)
2011	41,437.72	4,628.48	5554.17
2012	42,115.91	5,007.65	6009.18
2013	58,745.85	4,805.64	5766.77
2014	63,524.49	4,714.56	5657.47
2015	74,410.95	3,741.76	4490.11
2016	83,218.22	3,307.46	3968.95
2017	91,599.98	4,027.95	4833.53
2018	98,392.13	5,320.89	6385.07
2019	108,085.82	5,261.92	6314.30
2020	97,718.07	4,952.22	5942.67
2021	108,468.24	6,402.71	7683.25
2022	130,077.62	10,179.35	12215.22

Table 4.12: Summary Statistics of VAT Rate (20% Increment)

	VAT Rate
Mean	6235.0587
Standard Deviation	2114.575982
No. of years	12

The provided summary statistics indicate an average Value Added Tax (VAT) rate of approximately ₦6235.06 billion, with a standard deviation of around ₦2114.56 billion, over the 12 years, considering a 20% increment.

Figure 4.8: Graphical Representation of VAT Rate (20% Increment)

Table 4.13: Summary Statistics of the Simulated Consumer Spending (20% Increment)

<i>Simulated consumer spending</i>	
Number of Iterations	1000
Mean	85759.15651
Standard Deviation	2064.21406
Kurtosis	0.080898982
Skewness	-5.92881E-05
Minimum	78931.11963
Maximum	92999.54794

4.5.3 (a): Interpretation of Data

The sensitivity analysis, conducted with 1,000 iterations, examines consumer spending patterns in response to a 20% increase in VAT rates. The average simulated consumer spending is estimated at ₦85,759.16 billion, serving as a key indicator of expected average consumption under this scenario.

The standard deviation of approximately ₦2,064.21 billion highlights significant variation around the mean.

The kurtosis value of approximately 0.08 indicates a slightly platykurtic distribution, with a flatter peak and thinner tails compared to a normal distribution, suggesting fewer extreme values. Additionally, the skewness value, close to zero, reflects an almost symmetrical distribution of simulated consumer spending, indicating a balanced set of

results with minimal deviation from the mean.

4.5.3 (b): Changes in Linear relationship

The sensitivity analysis results indicate that the linear relationship model needs adjustment to account for the effects of a 20% increase in VAT rates. The revised model is expressed as:

$$CS = 7.7459155 * V + 34853.3473 + e$$

In this updated model, the slope has been adjusted to 7.7459, reflecting the new rate of change in consumer spending for each unit increase in the VAT rate. This adjustment accounts for the anticipated impact of the VAT rate increase.

The intercept remains at 34,853.35, representing the estimated consumer spending when the VAT rate is zero. Since the adjustment affects only the VAT rate's impact, the intercept value remains unchanged.

Figure 4.9: Graphical representation of Simulated Consumer Spending (20% Increment)

4.6 Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study offer a detailed understanding of the intricate relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) rate adjustments and consumer spending patterns in Nigeria. The research aims to:

1. Simulate and analyze the effects of varying VAT rates on consumer spending behavior.
2. Identify key factors influencing consumer responses to VAT rate changes.
3. Assess the significance of various variables affecting consumer spending simulations.
4. Evaluate potential policy implications based on observed consumer behaviour trends.

The study effectively used rigorous empirical analysis and Monte Carlo simulation techniques to simulate the impact of variable VAT rates on consumer spending behavior. By exploring multiple VAT rate scenarios, the study provided valuable insights into the range of consumer spending outcomes under different fiscal policy frameworks.

Through sensitivity analyses and empirical data examination, the study identified several critical variables that significantly affect consumer spending in response to VAT changes. It integrated both macroeconomic indicators and micro-level socio-economic variables, offering a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing consumer behavior.

Robust statistical analysis highlighted key variables that impacted the simulation model's performance. These variables, spanning economic, demographic, and policy-related characteristics, each contributed uniquely to observed consumer spending patterns.

The study also identified practical policy implications, providing evidence-based insights for strategic decision-making and policy formulation. It clarified the potential effects of VAT policy changes on consumer spending patterns and overall economic activity, supporting informed policy decisions.

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of Findings

i. The findings underscore the significant role of VAT rates in shaping consumer spending patterns in Nigeria. The positive linear relationship between VAT rates and consumer spending suggests that changes in VAT policy can substantially impact both consumer behavior overall economic activity.

ii. The initial descriptive analysis, covering a 12-year period from 2011 to 2022, revealed an upward trend in consumer spending alongside variations in VAT rates. Average consumer spending was approximately ₦83.15 billion with a standard deviation of ₦27.74 billion, indicating notable variability. The average VAT rate over this period was ₦5.196 billion with a standard deviation of ₦1.762 billion, reflecting fluctuations in fiscal policies.

iii. Monte Carlo simulations provided insights into potential consumer spending outcomes under various VAT rate scenarios. With 1,000 iterations, the simulations produced a range of possible outcomes, offering a comprehensive view of consumer spending patterns in response to random VAT rate variations.

iv. The mean simulated consumer spending was approximately ₦84,677.57 billion, with a standard deviation of ₦1,729.30 billion, indicating moderate variability. The negative skewness value (-0.128) suggested

a slight leftward skew in the distribution, while the kurtosis value (-0.005) indicated a platykurtic distribution with thinner tails compared to a normal distribution.

v. Sensitivity analyses assessed the impact of VAT rate increases (5%, 10%, and 20%) on consumer spending. The simulations revealed a range of mean simulated consumer spending from approximately ₦83,335.09 billion to ₦85,759.16 billion, depending on the VAT increment. Variability, kurtosis, and skewness were also evaluated under different VAT scenarios.

vi. The sensitivity analysis highlights the importance of evaluating various VAT rate increments to understand their effects on consumer spending. These findings emphasize the need for policymakers to carefully consider the potential impacts of VAT rate adjustments on households and the broader economy, as even minor changes in VAT rates can significantly influence consumer spending.

vii. The linear relationship model indicates a positive correlation between VAT rates and consumer spending. For every one-unit increase in the VAT rate, consumer spending is expected to rise by approximately ₦9.30 billion, assuming other factors remain constant.

5.2 Conclusions

Based on the analysis conducted in the study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

There is a positive linear relationship between VAT rates and consumer spending in Nigeria. An increase in VAT rates is associated with a corresponding increase in consumer spending, assuming other factors remain constant.

Adjustments in VAT policy have a considerable impact on consumer spending

patterns and overall economic activity in Nigeria. Changes in VAT rates can lead to significant shifts in consumer behaviour and economic dynamics.

The Monte Carlo simulations offer valuable insights into the range of potential consumer spending outcomes under varying VAT rate scenarios. These simulations underscore the unpredictability and variability in consumer responses to changes in VAT policy.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

Policymakers should carefully evaluate the potential impacts of any modifications to VAT rates on both households and the broader economy. Understanding how changes in VAT policy affect consumer spending patterns and overall economic activity is crucial for informed decision-making.

Continuous efforts should be made to collect and analyze comprehensive data on VAT rates and consumer spending patterns in Nigeria. Accurate, up-to-date statistics are essential for formulating effective policies. Additionally, further sensitivity analyses should be conducted to explore the impacts of varying VAT rate increases on consumer spending, providing deeper insights into different policy scenarios.

There should be increased public awareness and education campaigns focused on VAT policy and its effects on consumer spending. Improving public understanding can foster greater transparency and communication between consumers and stakeholders, leading to more informed and engaged responses to VAT policy changes.

5.4 Contributions to Knowledge

This study significantly enhances the existing body of knowledge by

investigating the impact of Value Added Tax (VAT) rate changes on consumer spending patterns in Nigeria. The study addresses a critical gap in the literature by offering empirical data on how variations in VAT rates influence consumer spending behavior. Key contributions include:

- i. The study provides detailed data on how Nigerian consumers adjust their spending habits in response to VAT rate changes, offering new insights into consumer behaviour and economic activity in the Nigerian context.
- ii. By incorporating concepts from behavioral economics, particularly intertemporal choice theory, the study deepens the theoretical understanding of the psychological factors driving consumer spending decisions.
- iii. The application of simulation modeling to evaluate the effects of VAT rate changes represents an innovative approach, expanding the methodological toolkit available for studying VAT-related impacts. This approach offers policymakers a robust analytical framework to consider when designing and implementing tax policies.

5.5 Suggestions for future research

To build on the findings of this study and address its limitations, future research could explore the following avenues:

- i. Conducting thorough evaluations of the impacts of VAT policy changes on consumer spending patterns and overall economic activity would offer valuable data for policymakers. Comparing the effectiveness of different VAT policy scenarios through detailed analysis can help refine policy decisions and improve their outcomes.
- ii. Future research could examine how VAT rate changes affect different demographic groups within Nigeria, such as various income levels, age

groups, or geographic regions. Understanding these variations can provide a more comprehensive view of how VAT policy impacts diverse segments of the population.

- iii. Comparing the effects of VAT rate changes in Nigeria with other countries that have implemented similar policies could provide a broader perspective on the potential outcomes and effectiveness of different VAT strategies.

5.6 Limitations of the Study:

One limitation of the study is its narrow focus on the relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) rates and consumer spending patterns, neglecting to analyze the broader macroeconomic implications of these changes. Macroeconomic indicators like Gross Domestic Product (GDP), consumer price index (CPI), and interest rates, which are critical for understanding the overall economic landscape, were not included in the analysis.

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